

LIAISON's achievements

Better Rural Innovation: Linking Actors, Instruments and Policies through Networks (LIAISON), Horizon2020, 2018-2022, RIA GA no. 773418)

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LIAISON's evidence base on co-innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural areas

- Analyses based on various types of multi-actor projects
 - Light-touch reviews (200)
 - In-depth case studies (32)
<https://liaison2020.eu/our-network/case-studies/>
- ,Under the radar' projects, networks or initiatives
 - European Rural Innovation Contest organised with 175 profiles on the interactive map
<https://liaison2020.eu/our-network/ambassadors/>
 - Awarding of 15 Rural Innovation Ambassadors, production of 15 Ambassador + 1 Journey videos, incl. translation of subtitles
<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC6EKMM7Gh4wkhfA98RK9AMg>
 - Wide use of the Ambassador videos: Broadcasting by a rural TV-Show in Romania; used as introduction at national/EU conferences, seminars etc.

Practice recommendations: Management of co-innovation processes and facilitation of a group events

<https://liaison2020.eu/your-material/?language=english>

LIAISON How-to-Guides (5)

- Coming Together
- Good Planning
- Healthy Partnerships
- Connected Partnerships
- Achieving Impact

Tool box Guides (2)

- Participatory Methods for Facilitating Co-innovation Projects
- Evaluation and Impact Assessment of Co-Innovation

Translated and language edited:
BG, DE, ES, FR, HU, IT, PL, RO

Lessons learnt

- Co-innovation can occur in projects funded by many public and private sources. It can be achieved not only through projects but also through other 'actor configurations' such as value chain partnerships, networks, clusters and programmes.
- Projects are 'temporary organisations' based on partnership or consortia that engage with a 'larger periphery' of stakeholders. As small innovation systems, they need access to all necessary expertise but *not necessary as part of the core consortium*.
- These partnerships share knowledge and partners. Partners bring their acquired knowledge with them from one partnership to another. All these partnerships are 'sharing the space' in the AKIS.
- The co-innovation process in projects/networks can contribute to building the capacity of the AKIS.
- Partnerships are not formed solely in response to calls for proposals, but as a result of different 'triggers'. This can influence the partnership structure and factors such as the design of the decision-making processes.
- Actors have different motivations for participating in co-innovation and for forming consortia. Definition of objectives, engagement with nature and recognition of benefits evolve because they result from constant negotiation between partners.

Policy recommendations: “Roadmap to levelling up the EIP-AGRI - a Common Framework for functional Capacity Development in EU MS” (LIAISON Policy Brief2)

- EU policy engagement: Ongoing contribution to the SCAR-AKIS working group (written - mandate report, oral/PPT - meetings)
- It's evident, lots of progress has been made with the EIP-AGRI implementation since 2012
- But several improvements remain challenging.
- LIAISON's insights from its field work and the work on the Common Framework on CD show that we need to **think bigger and keep an eye on the complexity of the EIP-AGRI implementation**, and the related **functional capacities** of all actors involved.
- Even when challenging: strong national policy engagement in several EU MS such as BG, RO, PL, UK, DE...

- LIAISON policy recommendations PPT and published policy briefs (10)
- Other types of policy interaction, EU and national level (57)

Dissemination and exploitation at a glance

- Web-based output: [LIAISON website](#), [LIAISON Twitter account](#), [Zenodo liaisonh2020 community](#), Participatory tools (homepage in FR by [IDELE](#)); Partner homepages; Practice [Abstracts](#) on the EIP-AGRI platform (45); [Training Module](#) for the How-to-Guides; [Videos on YouTube](#); [Evaluation/SelfAssessment tools](#)
- Published Scientific papers (15); more under development
- Numerous practice papers: Result flyer, articles in newsletters, blogs, homepage entries or professional media
- Workshops organised at LIAISON events (16)
- LIAISON workshops at events of others (26)
- Contributions to conferences/workshops of others (29)

Potential impact on the target groups

Project results
/ Outputs

Outcomes of a
project

Impact

1. LIAISON teams are very likely to realise outcome and impact because first indications of evidence become visible. Outcomes and impact will refer to and depend very much on the
 - around 45 participants (actors) in LIAISON;
 - diverse group of co-innovation practitioners using LIAISON's practice-related material;
 - administrative staff, farm advisors or other innovation support service providers using LIAISON's practice-related material;
 - policy makers on the EU and national/regional level using the policy briefs and/or the practice-related material.
2. Particular lessons learnt for the translation of practice-relevant output
3. Bonding with the family of multi-actor projects (EIP-AGRI, others)
4. Engagement with and for SMEs in the EIP-Agri context